

Effect of local environment and stellar mass on galaxy quenching at $0.5 < z < 2.0$ in ZFOURGE/CANDELS

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collaborations**

- Near-IR galaxy survey with FourStar instrument on Magellan
- Accurate and robust redshifts with $\sim 2\%$ accuracy for $\sim 60,000$ galaxies at $z > 1$.

The advantage of deep NIR imaging with medium-band filters for finding large-scale structure at $z \sim 2$

Measuring galaxy overdensities with ZFOURGE photometric redshifts

The Bayesian-motivated 3rd nearest neighbor of local surface density of a galaxy (Ivezić+05):

$$\Sigma'_3 = C \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^3 d_i^2}$$

A galaxy overdensity:

$$(1 + \delta)_3 = 1 + \frac{\Sigma_3 - \langle \Sigma \rangle}{\langle \Sigma \rangle}$$

Selection of quiescent and star-forming galaxies

Higher quiescent fraction in denser environment

Environmental quenching efficiency: excess in quiescent fraction compared to the low-density at a given mass

$$\varepsilon_{\text{env}}(\delta, \delta_0, M) = \frac{f_q(\delta, M) - f_q(\delta_0, M)}{1 - f_q(\delta_0, M)}$$

See also van den Bosch +08, Peng+10, Quadri+12, Kovač+14

Dependence of environmental quenching on stellar mass and redshift

Low-mass galaxies: Minimal environmental quenching at $z > 1.5$, and its increasing contribution toward low- z .

Dependence of environmental quenching on stellar mass and redshift

More massive galaxies: significant ($\sim 30\%$) environmental quenching for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$, and remain roughly constant toward low- z

Dependence of environmental quenching on stellar mass and redshift

Stellar mass and environmental quenching are largely separable (at low- z , see Peng+10, Kovač+14) and out to $z \sim 3$ (e.g. Quadri+12) but limited to $M > 10^{10} M_{\odot}$

Dependence of environmental quenching on stellar mass and redshift

Effects of quenching related to (stellar) mass and environment are not separable

Dependence of environmental quenching on stellar mass and redshift

consistent with “overconsumption” model (McGee+14)
—> exhaustion of a gas reservoir through star formation and outflows.

Dependence of environmental quenching on stellar mass and redshift

At low- z , quenching time scale predicted by overconsumption model becomes long ($\sim 10\text{Gyr}$). Other dynamical processes in halo may become more important at $z < 1$ (Balogh+16)

Environmental quenching vs. mass quenching

Mass quenching:

$$\epsilon_{\text{mass}}(M, M_0, \delta) = \frac{f_q(\delta, M) - f_q(\delta, M_0)}{1 - f_q(\delta, M_0)}$$

See also van den Bosch+08, Peng+10, Quadri+12, Kovač+14

Environmental quenching vs. mass quenching

Majority of low-mass quiescent galaxies are quenched by their environment (see Hogg+03, Quadri+12).

Environmental quenching vs. mass quenching

For more massive galaxies, in high-density environment, effects of quenching related to stellar mass and environment are comparable

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$8.8 < \log(M/M_{\odot}) < 9.8$ at $0.5 < z < 1.0$

The morphological parameters measured by van der Wel+12 using the HST/WFC3 F160W imaging.

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$8.8 < \log(M/M_{\odot}) < 9.8$ at $0.5 < z < 1.0$

There is no strong evidence that **quiescent galaxies** in low- and high-density have different morphologies

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$8.8 < \log(M/M_{\odot}) < 9.8$ at $0.5 < z < 1.0$

Star-forming δ_{75}
Star-forming δ_{25}
Quiescent δ_{75}
Quiescent δ_{25}

Quiescent galaxies in high-density environments have different structural properties than **SF'ing galaxies** — environmental quenching must transform galaxy morphologies

Quiescent fraction

Quiescent fraction

Sérsic index

Quiescent fraction/Sérsic index

at the highest densities the **quiescent fraction** of low-mass galaxies is **changing faster** than the Sérsic index.

$0.5 < z < 1.0$

$1.0 < z < 1.5$

$1.5 < z < 2.0$

Quiescent fraction/Sérsic index

at the highest densities the **quiescent fraction** of low-mass galaxies is **changing faster** than the Sérsic index.

Summary

- The advantage of accurate photo-z and the depth of ZFOURGE for measuring local galaxy environment out to $z \sim 2$, extended to low-mass galaxies ($10^{9.5} M_{\odot}$)
- Minimal environmental quenching for low-mass galaxies at $z > 1.5$, and it eventually dominates (stellar) mass quenching in dense environment at low- z .
- Effects of quenching related to (stellar) mass and environment are not separable
- Environmental quenching also transforms galaxy morphologies

Measuring galaxy overdensities with ZFOURGE photometric redshifts vs. spectroscopic redshifts from a mock galaxy catalog

Correlation coefficient

Contamination at high-density environment:

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{phot}}] > \delta_{75} [z_{\text{phot}}]$ and also $\delta [z_{\text{spec}}] < \delta_{50} [z_{\text{spec}}]$

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{phot}}] > \delta_{75} [z_{\text{phot}}]$

Contamination at low-density environment:

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{phot}}] < \delta_{25} [z_{\text{phot}}]$ and $\delta [z_{\text{spec}}] > \delta_{50} [z_{\text{spec}}]$

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{phot}}] < \delta_{25} [z_{\text{phot}}]$

Bayesian 3rd NN

Traditional 3rd NN

Completeness at high-density environment:

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{phot}}] > \delta_{75} [z_{\text{phot}}]$ and also $\delta [z_{\text{spec}}] > \delta_{50} [z_{\text{spec}}]$

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{spec}}] > \delta_{75} [z_{\text{spec}}]$

Completeness at low-density environment:

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{phot}}] < \delta_{25} [z_{\text{phot}}]$ and $\delta [z_{\text{spec}}] < \delta_{50} [z_{\text{spec}}]$

galaxies with $\delta [z_{\text{spec}}] < \delta_{25} [z_{\text{spec}}]$

Bayesian 3rd NN

Traditional 3rd NN

Evolution of environmental quenching

Minimal environmental quenching ($\approx 5\%$) for low-mass galaxies at $z > 1.5$, and increasing toward low- z .

Evolution of environmental quenching

Significant ($\sim 30\%$) environmental quenching for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$, and remain roughly constant toward low- z

Star-forming δ_{75}
 Star-forming δ_{25}
 Quiescent δ_{75}
 Quiescent δ_{25}

Star-forming δ_{75}
 Star-forming δ_{25}
 Quiescent δ_{75}
 Quiescent δ_{25}

Stellar mass density in 1kpc

Kawinwanichakij+17

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$8.8 < \log(M/M_{\odot}) < 9.8$ at $0.5 < z < 1.0$

Sérsic index

$\text{Log}(R_{\text{eff}})$

Axis ratio

Stellar mass
density in 1 kpc

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$$\log(M/M_{\odot}) > 10.5 \text{ at } 0.5 < z < 1.0$$

Likelihood that samples have same parent distribution from K-S test

■ K-S (Q galaxies in low- and high-density)

□ K-S (Q and SF galaxies in high-density)

Reject (at $>3\sigma$) the hypothesis that morphologies of Q and SF are drawn from the same parent distribution

The quiescent galaxies in low- and high-density have the same parent distribution

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$$9.8 < \log(M/M_{\odot}) < 10.5 \text{ at } 0.5 < z < 1.0$$

Likelihood that samples have same parent distribution from K-S test

■ K-S (Q galaxies in low- and high-density)

□ K-S (Q and SF galaxies in high-density)

Morphologies of Q and SF in high-density are different

No (or at best, weak evidence) that quiescent galaxies in low- and high-density have different morphologies

On the Environmental Impact on Morphology

$$8.8 < \log(M/M_{\odot}) < 9.8 \text{ at } 0.5 < z < 1.0$$

Likelihood that samples have same parent distribution from K-S test

 K-S (Q galaxies in low- and high-density)

 K-S (Q and SF galaxies in high-density)

Environmental quenching also transform galaxies morphologies

- Near-IR galaxy survey with FourStar instrument on Magellan
- Accurate and robust redshifts with $\sim 2\%$ accuracy for $\sim 60,000$ galaxies at $z > 1$.

Credit: Adam Tomczak

Measuring galaxy overdensities with ZFOURGE photometric redshifts

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A galaxy overdensity:

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Galaxy overdensity

What processes could be driving environmental quenching?

- At $z > 1$, environmental quenching efficiency increases with stellar mass \rightarrow consistent with “overconsumption” model (McGee+14)
- The quenching time predicted by overconsumption model become too long (~ 10 Gyr)
 - \rightarrow other dynamical processes become dominate (Balogh+16).
 - \rightarrow constant environmental quenching with stellar mass at $z < 1$ as observed here and other studies (e.g., Peng+10, Quadri+12, Kovač+14)